

*Papalite
Speaks*

**Papal Seminary:
A Second Home and a Place of Happiness**

Ajesh Marappilal

Papal Seminary, with a lot of love we call “Home of Love” was really a home of love for me. I, Fr. Ajesh Marappilal, am a priest of the Syro-Malabar Catholic Diocese of Kothamangalam. I had my theological studies at Papal Seminary from 2011 to 2014. When I reflect on my life at Papal Seminary, the first thought that comes to my mind is a feeling of happiness because the Papal Seminary was a place where I experienced the true value of happiness.

I reached Papal Seminary on 27th May 2011. When we arrived, two persons had come from the seminary in a jeep to receive us. We did not know them and we thought they were workers because they simply carried our luggage to the jeep. The next fine day morning when I went for the mass in the chapel, I saw the same man who carried my luggage on the previous day at the altar celebrating mass for us. It was really a shocking experience for me. I realised that it was Fr. Jacob Kulangara, SJ, the minister of the house. For me, it was an eye-opening and shocking experience. This experience redefined my concept of a priest as well as of a formator. Throughout the formation in the Papal Seminary, it was a continuation of that initial experience. I could see a good member of highly knowledgeable, humble, sincere, loving and caring human beings. The basic call that I received from Papal Seminary was of being a good human being and the call to be a good priest was secondary only. The whole Papal community had the true realisation that being a good human is the sole criterion for being a good priest.

My life in Papal Seminary was enriched primarily by the presence of a good number of excellent human beings. First and foremost, I would like to recall Fr. Jose Thayil, SJ, our Rector. A person of true integrity, simplicity, humility and holiness. I was really taken up by the way he corrected us. One day, a Saturday morning which was a day of monthly recollection, we are supposed to maintain silence. But there was a lot of noise

in the refectory. By hearing the noise, Fr. Jose came to the refectory and without even raising his head he just walked through the refectory. This simple act communicated a lot to me. I felt it was a way of enforcing discipline without hurting individuals. I can narrate pages and pages about the qualities of our rector that attracted me and often fascinated me. Since he is also from Kerala whenever he comes for holidays the way he interacts with us became a point of envy for other seminarians. The humble presence of Father in the long corridors of Papal Seminary was a true inspiration and a solace of hope for me.

Without mentioning the name of Fr. Paul Raj, any of my memories of Papal Seminary will not be complete. He was such a true guide, mentor, and a real elder brother to me. He was my living group animator, the animator of *Petras*, our living group. He was my animator during my 4th year of theology also. What attracts me to him is his genuine nature. He always tried to be true to himself. It means that he never tried to hide anything from us. If he felt bad about something, he used to tell us directly. I always found that as a great human value. Personal sharings, living group meetings, group dynamics, living group gatherings, etc. all are still cherished in my mind. Finally, in my first mass, his presence on the altar was really a source of strength.

The three questions and answers of beloved Fr. Kurian, SJ, and the holy smiling presence of Fr. Noel, SJ, really added colour to my life in Papal Seminary. Fr. Jacob our minister was a true friend and an elder brother to me. I cannot forget the encouragement and moments of fun we had together.

Another inspiring and loving presence was my dear loving Fr. V.M. Jose, SJ. I think I had the freedom to go to him at any time for anything. He always listened to me with a smiling face. He never came to any of us as a professor or a great formator; instead, he was a great caring and loving friend to us. That inspired me a lot.

How can I forget Fr. Vincent Crasta, SJ my spiritual director who has showed me a different way of looking at spiritual life. The first word in all my confessions with him was “Ajesh, Rejoice in the Lord always.” This was a great source of inspiration. Fr. Vincent helped me to understand the real meaning of spiritual direction.

Fr. Nishant is a person with great memories. He helped me a lot with how to formulate arguments, how to present them before the community. He was the animator of the Theology Students’ Council, while I was the

president. Fr. Paul Parathazham was another person with a lot of happy memories. Both of us are from the same diocese so that was a point of pride for me. I used to run for his classes and lectures because those were such inspiring. If I go on writing about the persons who had inspired me it will go on for pages.

Along with the persons, the community was a happy one. I always had a positive influence on the community. The prime point was that it was rich in encouraging others and accepting them. All were exemplary in accepting the other as they were. I could find people who were trying to live as authentic human beings. The bond we shared in the group, in the batch with the animators, staff and other brothers was excellent. The true bond between philosophers and theologians we had in Papal Seminary enabled us to cross all barriers of age and that united us as one true family. Nobody tried to dominate the others and instead, everybody mutually helped the other and that was a source of inspiration for all of us.

The spiritual freedom we had in our seminary days moulded us in spirituality. Nobody was compelling us there for anything, but it was quite normal for us to see a good number of people in the domestic chapel even in the late midnights. The living group, spiritual sharing, spiritual conferences, group prayers, daily masses and all other spiritual activities helped me to grow spiritually in a very personal way. The spiritual transformation of the seminarians was gradual and an independent process. The formation never tried to impose anything on us instead it was an attempt to create deep-rooted convictions. So, the convictions that we took along with us to the ministry from the home of love gradually transformed into the powerhouse of our priestly life. Often in the formation houses what happens is that they impose so many restrictions to create a spiritual routine. But, in effect, sometimes that becomes futile. But the spiritual formation of the seminarians that happens in the Papal Seminary is a process of enabling the person to be rooted in Christ. Papal Seminary gave a solid foundation for my spiritual life.

The community life was an experience of joy and happiness. It was a community where I could be myself. It remains the unique feature of Papal Seminary. When I was there, I used to hear from old students that it was really a place of love. When I left the place, I really understood the meaning of it. Papal Seminary is really a home of love. If you ask me which is the happiest time in your life. Without a doubt, I would say that it is the years that I spent in Papal Seminary. It is a second home, and it is the place that I

want to come back always. My dear Papalites, we are all one. The warmth and joy that we share is the uniqueness of our home.

About the Author

Fr. Ajesh George Marappillil, a Catholic Priest belongs to the Syro Malabar Catholic Diocese of Kothamangalam, Kerala, India. His theological formation was at Papal Seminary Pune and obtained B.Th. in 2014 from Jnana Deepa Pune. He holds a BA in philosophy from Mahatma Gandhi University Kottayam, Kerala, MA in History from Sree Sankaracharya University Kerala and MA in Political Science from IGNOU. He holds an M.Phil. in History from Bharathidasan University Tiruchirappalli and an MBA from Pondicherry Central University. He is currently pursuing a PhD at Bharathidasan University Tiruchirappalli.